

RESEARCH ON CENTRAL ASIAN SUFI SCHOLARS IN THE TURKISH ACADEMIC SPHERE

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Abstract: *The article analyzes the study of Central Asian Sufi orders’ scholars and their scholarly heritage within the Turkish academic sphere. It highlights the research of Turkish Islamic scholars on Sufi figures such as Ahmad Yasawi, Najmiddin Kubra, and Bahouddin Naqshband. Furthermore, it examines the scientific role of the Yasawiyya, Kubraviyya, and Naqshbandiyya orders in the formation of Sufism studies in Turkey, including their contributions to source studies, textual scholarship, and the preservation of spiritual heritage. The article presents the scholarly investigations of Turkish researchers from the 20th century to the present using historical and analytical approaches. The findings contribute to strengthening scientific collaboration between Central Asia and Turkey.*

Keywords: *Turkey, Central Asia, Sufism, Naqshbandiyya, Yasawiyya, Kubraviyya, Ahmad Yasawi, Bahouddin Naqshband, scholarly research, source studies, Sufism studies.*

TURKIYA ILMİY MUHITIDA MARKAZIY OSIYO TASAVVUF ALLOMALARI TADQIQI

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Annotatsiya: *Maqolada Turkiya ilmiy muhitida Markaziy Osiyo tasavvuf tariqatlari allomalari va ularning ilmiy merosini o‘rganish jarayoni tahlil etilgan. Jumladan, turkiyalik islomshunos olimlarning Ahmad Yassaviy, Najmiddin Kubro, Bahouddin Naqshband kabi mutasavviflar haqidagi tadqiqotlari yoritilgan. Shuningdek, Turkiyada tasavvufshunoslik fani shakllanishida Yassaviyya, Kubraviyya va Naqshbandiyya tariqatlarining ilmiy o‘rni, manbashunoslik, matnshunoslik va ma’naviy merosni saqlashdagi roli ochib berilgan. Maqolada XX asrdan hozirgi kungacha davom etayotgan turkiyalik tadqiqotchilarning ilmiy*

izlanishlari tarixiy va tahliliy yondashuv asosida taqdim etilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari Markaziy Osiyo va Turkiya o’rtasidagi ilmiy hamkorlikni yanada mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit soʻzlar: *Turkiya, Markaziy Osiyo, tasavvuf, Naqshbandiyya, Yassaviyya, Kubraviyya, Ahmad Yassaviy, Bahouddin Naqshband, ilmiy tadqiqotlar, manbashunoslik, tasavvufshunoslik.*

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОАЗИАТСКИХ СУФИЙСКИХ УЧЁНЫХ В ТУРЕЦКОЙ АКАДЕМИЧЕСКОЙ СРЕДЕ

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Аннотация: *В статье анализируется процесс изучения учёных Центральноазиатских суфийских орденов и их научного наследия в турецкой академической среде. Особое внимание уделено исследованиям турецких исламоведов о суфийских деятелях, таких как Ахмад Ясави, Наджмиддин Кубра и Бахууддин Накибанд. Кроме того, рассматривается научная роль орденов Ясавийя, Кубравийя и Накибандийя в формировании суфиеведения в Турции, включая их вклад в источниковедение, текстологию и сохранение духовного наследия. В статье представлены научные исследования турецких исследователей с XX века до настоящего времени на основе историко-аналитического подхода. Результаты способствуют укреплению научного сотрудничества между Центральной Азией и Турцией.*

Ключевые слова: *Турция, Центральная Азия, суфизм, Накибандийя, Ясавийя, Кубравийя, Ахмад Ясави, Бахууддин Накибанд, научные исследования, источниковедение, суфиеведение.*

INTRODUCTION

The contributions of Turkish scholars to the study of Central Asian Sufi orders, their leading figures, and their intellectual heritage are of exceptional significance. By the 20th century, the field of Sufi studies underwent a profound transformation, marked by both methodological shifts and ideological tensions. In particular, alongside the recognition and appreciation of Sufi scholars, processes of

marginalization and denigration also emerged, a trend that persisted throughout the Soviet period¹.

Under such circumstances, Turkey served as a crucial intellectual and cultural refuge, preserving the esteemed legacy, reputation, and scholarly heritage of Central Asian Sufi figures. This phenomenon was shaped by two principal factors. First, Turkey’s own historical and religious traditions positioned Sufism at the center of scholarly inquiry. Second, the shared cultural and historical roots of Turkic peoples naturally directed academic attention toward the Sufi schools of Central Asia².

The convergence of these factors facilitated the expansion of research in Turkey on Central Asian Sufi sheikhs, Sufi orders, and related textual traditions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In particular, the study of the intellectual legacy of Ahmad Yassawi, a prominent representative of the Turkic Sufi tradition, was consistently continued in Turkey. This was not a случайный development. As repeatedly emphasized by Turkish scholars, the consolidation of Islam in Anatolia, as well as the improvement of social, economic, and spiritual life, was significantly influenced by the teachings of Khoja Ahmad Yassawi and the activities of the Yassawiyya dervishes.

In Turkey, the role of Muhammad Fuad Köprülü³ in the study of Sufi orders and, in particular, the intellectual heritage of Ahmad Yassawi, is of exceptional importance. It is well known that his work “*Early Mystics in Turkish Literature*”⁴, published in 1918, marked a turning point in Yassawi studies. It must be acknowledged that, to this day, neither in Turkey nor in other regions inhabited by Turkic peoples has another study achieved a level of recognition comparable to that of Köprülü’s work.

¹ Abdurasulov Sh. Annemarie Schimmel asarlarida Markaziy Osiyo tasavvuf allomalari va ularning ilmiy merosi tahlili // International Scientific-Practical Conference “Historical realities and philosophical ideals: dialogues across disciplines”. — Tashkent: Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies, 2025. — B. 399–410.

² Abdurasulov Sh., Doniyorov A. Markaziy Osiyo tasavvuf tarixining nemis olimi Yurgen Paul tomonidan tadqiqi: Naqshbandiyya misolida // XXI asr: fan va ta’lim masalalari. — 2025. — №3. — B. 307–321.

³ One of Turkey’s leading scholars, Fuad Köprülü, was born on December 4, 1890, in Istanbul. He was an influential Turkish statesman, serving as the Minister of Foreign Affairs, and was also active as a philologist, historian, and publicist. His family lineage traces back, in the tenth generation, to the Grand Vizier Köprülü Mehmed Pasha. After graduating from the Ayasofya Central Secondary School in Istanbul’s Yerebatan district, he continued his education at Mercan High School. During his years at Mercan Lyceum, he studied Persian, Arabic, and French. Subsequently, through extensive reading—particularly of Western intellectuals—he sought to broaden his intellectual horizons. Fuad Köprülü passed away on June 28, 1966, in Istanbul.

⁴ Fuad Köprülü. Türk edebiyatında ilk mutasavvıflar. – Ankara: Türk Tarih Kurumu Basımevi, 1976. – 412 s..

The renowned Ottoman Turkish poet Yahya Kemal⁵ once addressed the distinguished scholar Muhammad Fuad Köprülü with the following words: “*Study deeply the mysteries of Ahmad Yassawi’s legacy. There you will find the foundations of our national identity.*” Inspired by this appeal, Köprülü embarked upon a systematic study of the life and works of Ahmad Yassawi. As a result of his long-term research, in 1919, he published his seminal work *Early Mystics in Turkish Literature*, on which he had worked for more than five years and which brought him international recognition.

This work opened new horizons not only in the study of Turkish literature but also within the broader field of Turkology, as it addressed a wide range of issues related to Turkish history. The book provides extensive information on the lives and works of two major figures and is structured into two main parts.

In the first part, following a general overview of Turkish literature and the spread of Islam among the Turks prior to Ahmad Yassawi, as well as the development of the Sufi movement, detailed information is presented on the legendary and historical life of Ahmad Yassawi, his Sufi order, his disciples (khalifas), and his literary and spiritual legacy.

The second part of the book is devoted to the renowned Turkish poet Yunus Emre. It provides a detailed account of his legendary life and examines the influence of his poetry. The enduring popularity of this work and its continued readership are not coincidental. The author successfully demonstrates that Ahmad Yassawi was the first to establish a Sufi tradition among Turkic peoples, which remained spiritually influential for centuries⁶.

In subsequent years, Fuad Köprülü continued his scholarly contributions to the field of Islamic studies. In particular, he completed his work “*History of Turkish Literature*”⁷ in 1921. Thereafter, in 1922–1923, he produced a series of important studies, including “*Islam in Anatolia*”⁸, “*The Origins of Bektashism*”, and “*The Influence of Turko-Mongol Shamanism on Islamic Sufi Sects*”, thereby making a significant contribution to the study of Turkish religious history.

In his work “*The Influence of Turko-Mongol Shamanism on Islamic Sufi Sects*”, Köprülü elucidates the impact of pre-Islamic shamanistic beliefs and modes of thought – considered an essential component of the national spiritual heritage of Muslim Turks – on the formation and development of Turkic Sufi concepts.

⁵ <https://www.inkilap.com/blog/icerik/yahya-kemal-beyatli>

⁶ M.Fuad Köprülü. Türk edebiyatında ilk mutasavvıflar. – Ankara: Türk Tarih Kurumu Basımevi, 1976. – 412 s.

⁷ M.Fuad Köprülü. Türk edebiyati tarihi. – İstanbul: Otuken, 1980. 405 s.

⁸ M.Fuad Köprülü. Anadolu’da İslâmiyet. – Ankara, 2005. 143 s.

DISCUSSION

It should be emphasized that between the 1930s and the 1970s, a certain stagnation prevailed in Turkey in the study of Ahmad Yassawi’s works. During this period, research activity slowed due to limited scientific resources, difficulties in working with manuscripts, and broader political and economic constraints. Nevertheless, scholarly interest in Yassawi’s legacy did not cease, and Turkish researchers continued to engage with his works on a regular basis.

As a result, in 1983, Professor Kemal Eraslan published “*Selections from the Divan-i Hikmat*”⁹. This work held significant importance for the academic community, as it introduced a new methodological approach to the systematic processing and presentation of Yassawi’s hikmats. In preparing the edition, Eraslan utilized nine manuscript sources and three printed versions, thereby enabling an integrated application of textual criticism, source analysis, and historical-contextual interpretation. The publication also included an extensive introduction of approximately fifty pages, detailed annotations, and a glossary, while the information provided about the individuals mentioned in the hikmats carried particular scholarly value.

It is important to note that Eraslan’s edition served as a foundational reference for subsequent studies. For instance, the book “*Hikmats of Ahmad Yassawi*”, prepared in 1991 by the Uzbek literary scholar Ibrahim Haqul, was based directly on Eraslan’s work. This demonstrates the intellectual interconnectedness between the scholarly environments of Turkey and Central Asia, as well as the regional and transnational significance of Yassawi’s legacy. At the same time, these studies made it possible to examine Yassawi’s works not only from historical and cultural perspectives but also within the frameworks of textual studies, source criticism, and Sufi studies.

In subsequent periods, research on the history of Sufism in Turkey, including the study of the intellectual heritage of Central Asian Sufi figures, continued without interruption. In particular, scholars such as Mahmud Asad Coşan¹⁰, Mehmed Zahid Kotku¹¹, Said al-Jazari¹², and Usman Turar¹³ produced numerous works addressing the fundamental nature of Sufism. Some of these works have also been translated into Uzbek.

⁹ Eraslan K. Ahmed-i Yesevî. Divan-ı Hikmet’ten seçmeler. — Ankara: Kültür Bakanlığı Yayınları, 1983. — 262 s.

¹⁰ <https://kh-davron.uz/kutubxona/islomiya-adabiyot/tasavvuf/mahmud-asad-joshon-haqqiy-sevgi.html>

¹¹ Muhammad Zâhid Kotku. Nefs nedir? – İstanbul: Erkam Yayınları, 1980. – 128 s.

(O‘zbekcha nashr: Nafs nimadir? – Toshkent: Sharq nashriyoti, 2020. Tarjima: Zebunisso Husayn qizi.)

¹² Umar Foruq Saydo al-Jazariy (1954) - turkiyalik Naqshbandiya tariqati ustozlaridan.

¹³ Usmon Turar. Tasavvuf tarixi. – Toshkent: Istiqlol nashriyoti, 1999. – 180 b.

Among them is Usman Turar’s book “*History of Sufism*” It can be regarded as an important reference for understanding the origins of Sufism. The work was published in Istanbul in 1999. It provides detailed and engaging information on various Sufi orders, particularly those widely распространённые in Central Asia, such as the Yassawiyya, Kubrawiyya, and Naqshbandiyya, including their origins and leading representatives. The second part of the book is specifically devoted to these Sufi orders. This significant work has also been translated into Uzbek. The translation was carried out by Nodirkhon Hasan, a researcher at the Alisher Navoi Institute of Language and Literature.

As noted above, the influence of Ahmad Yassawi’s творчество on Turkish literature and the spiritual world has also been emphasized by later Turkish scholars. Evidence of this can be found in the works of researchers such as Muhammad Sarhan Tayshi¹⁴, Ahmet Yaşar Ocak¹⁵, Mustafa Kara¹⁶, Usman Turar¹⁷, and Hasan Kamil Yılmaz¹⁸.

In particular, Mustafa Kara¹⁹ notes that the teachings of Ahmad Yassawi constituted a spiritual foundation of the Ottoman state. Meanwhile, Hasan Kamil Yılmaz²⁰, drawing on Evliya Çelebi’s *Seyahatname*, discusses the contributions of Yassawiyya followers to various crafts and professions.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Following the collapse of the Soviet system, the newly independent republics experienced a marked increase in interest in the personality and works of Ahmad Yassawi. The designation of 1993 as the “Year of Ahmad Yassawi” significantly intensified scholarly and public attention to the life, literary and spiritual activity, and legacy of this eminent Sufi figure, not only in Uzbekistan but also in other Turkic republics, particularly in Turkey.

Between 1991 and 1993, scholars from across the Turkic world organized a series of academic conferences in Uzbekistan and Turkey dedicated to Ahmad Yassawi, and the presented papers were subsequently published as collected volumes. In Turkey, several independent scholarly compilations were also issued. In addition, the Ahmad Yassawi Foundation was established, and its official publication, the journal *Yassawi*, began to be published.

¹⁴ Muhammad Sarxon Tayshiy. Ahmed-i Yesevi. Ahmed-i Yesevi's life-works-ideas-effects. –Istanbul: Seha, 1996, p. 51;

¹⁵ Ahmet Yaşar Ocak. "Anadolu sufiliğinde Ahmed-i Yesevi ve Yesevilik", Türk Dili, sayı: 204, Aralık 1993, 581-587.

¹⁶ <https://www.dergah.com.tr/yazarlar/mustafa-kara>.

¹⁷ Usmon Turar. Tasavvuf tarixi. – Toshkent: Istiqlol nashriyoti, 1999. – 180 b.

¹⁸ <https://hasankamilyilmaz.com/prof-dr-hasan-kamil-yilmaz-kimdir.html>

¹⁹ Mustafa Kara. Tasavvuf ve tarikatlar tarihi. – İstanbul: Dergâh Yayınları, 1995. – 304 s

²⁰ Hasan Kâmil Yılmaz. Tasavvuf ve tarikatlar. – İstanbul: Ensar Neşriyat, 1997. – 280 s.

A notable collection was compiled from the proceedings of conferences held in Istanbul and Izmir on May 1–2 and November 25–26, 1993. In the preface to this volume, Professor Mahmud As’ad Coşan, Doctor of Philological Sciences, emphasized that the work consists of substantial scholarly studies and academic reports on Ahmad Yassawi. He noted that it represents a highly valuable and significant contribution, filling a major gap in Yassawi studies and serving as a reliable source for researchers²¹. Indeed, several articles included in the volume attract particular attention due to their original approaches, interpretations, and analyses of Yassawi’s works, which warrants special emphasis.

It can also be noted that the articles included in the collection enrich the reader’s knowledge and understanding in two important respects. First, they address the geographical spread of the Yassawiyya order, extending from Central Asia westward to the Balkans, eastward to China, and northward to Moscow. Second, they examine the influence and position of Yassawi’s творчество in the development of pan-Turkic literature. These two issues have not yet been comprehensively studied as independent research topics.

Among Turkish scholars, the works of Mustafa Tahralı²² are particularly significant in addressing these questions. In his studies, the scholar refutes the view that Ahmad Yassawi’s creative legacy influenced only his immediate followers. Instead, he argues that it is difficult to find a prominent poet or writer in the history of Turkic literature who was not inspired by Yassawi’s words or who did not, in some form, draw upon the Sufi poetic tradition established by this great spiritual master.

In addition, during this period, “*Divan-i Hikmat*” was published by several scholars. Notably, in 2001, newly discovered hikmats of Ahmad Yassawi were published through the joint efforts of the Sayram-based historian Mirahmad Mirkholdoro’g’li and the Turkish scholar Professor Metin Okar²³.

In addition, studies on the figures of the Kubrawiyya and Naqshbandiyya orders and their intellectual heritage have also been conducted in Turkey. One of the Turkish scholars who examined the life of Najm al-Din Kubra and the principles of his Sufi order is Mustafa Kara²⁴. His works “*Türkistan’ın Işığ*” (*Necmeddin-i Kübra*) (“The Light of Turkestan: Najm al-Din Kubra”) and “*Necmeddin Kübra – Tasavvufî Hayat*”²⁵ (“Najm al-Din Kubra: A Sufi Life”),

²¹ Mahmud As’ad Jo’shon. İslâm, tasavvuf ve hayat. – İstanbul: Erkam Yayınları, 1996. – S 15-20.

²² <https://kubbealti.org.tr/kisi/mustafa-tahrali>

²³ Mirahmad Mirxoldoro’g’li; Metin Oqar. Hoca Ahmed Yesevî’nin yeni bulunan hikmetleri. – İstanbul: Kitapyurdu Yayınları, 2001. – 190 s.

²⁴ <https://www.dergah.com.tr/yazarlar/mustafa-kara>.

²⁵ Mustafa Kara. Necmeddin Kübra – Tasavvufî hayat. – Bursa: Dergâh Yayınları, 2000. – 215 s.

published in 2000, represent significant contributions to the study of Najm al-Din Kubra’s life and activities in Turkey.

The Naqshbandiyya order, as one of the most prominent Sufi traditions, continues to have adherents across the world, including in Turkey, where both practitioners and scholars actively engage in its study. One of the notable contemporary spiritual leaders and scholars associated with this tradition is Sheikh, Doctor, and Professor Mahmud As’ad Coşan²⁶. He is the author of more than thirty works on religious, legal (fiqh), and Sufi subjects, as well as over four hundred articles. Proficient in Arabic, Persian, English, and German, he traveled extensively across Central Asia, the Middle East, the United States, Japan, Germany, Denmark, Australia, and the Netherlands, delivering lectures and engaging in scholarly discussions on Islamic Sufism.

The book “*Gift of the Great Ones*”²⁷, compiled from twelve articles by the distinguished Sufi scholar Mahmud As’ad Coşan, has attracted considerable attention among researchers of Sufism. This work represents a selection of his writings, presenting teachings centered on love and spiritual refinement. It emphasizes that the essence of Islam lies not in conflict, disputes, or discord, but in goodness, compassion, and love. At the same time, it outlines the paths toward becoming a beloved servant of God and elaborates on the foundations of spiritual perfection.

In addition, the collection includes discussions on prominent figures of Central Asian Sufi orders. In particular, it provides extensive information on the lives and intellectual activities of leading Sufi figures such as Ahmad Yassawi, Najm al-Din Kubra, and Baha al-Din Naqshband.

Several notable works by the author have been published in Uzbekistan. The book “*Gift of the Great Ones*” is also well known among Uzbek readers interested in Sufism. It was translated into Uzbek by the young scholar Alimardon Hayitov and published by the Muharrir publishing house in 2012.

CONCLUSION

In the Turkish academic environment, the study of Central Asian Sufi schools – particularly the legacy of Ahmad Yassawi and his followers – has

²⁶ The ancestors of Sheikh Mahmud As’ad Coşan originate from Bukhara Sharif. He was born in 1938 in Çanakkale, a mountainous city located in the Asian part of Turkey. In terms of lineage, his family traces its roots to Bukhara Sharif, and genealogically he is considered a descendant of the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him), that is, a *sayyid*. Within the Naqshbandiyya spiritual chain, he is regarded as the 40th perfected spiritual guide (*murshid al-kamil*). A distinguished scholar proficient in the fields of tafsir, hadith, fiqh, theology, and Sufism, he was widely recognized for his role in the spiritual development of his students. Owing to his ability to cultivate spiritually mature disciples, he came to be known as *Shaykh al-Murabbi* (a spiritual guide who nurtures saints). He passed away in 2001 in Australia, where he spent the final years of his life.

²⁷ Mahmud As’ad Jo’shon. *Buyuklar tuhfası*. – Toshkent: Muharrir nashriyoti, 2012. – 220 b.

developed into a well-established scholarly tradition since the early twentieth century. The research of M. Fuad Köprülü laid the foundation for this process, as he systematically examined Yassawi’s works within historical, textual, and religious-philosophical contexts. His studies transformed Yassawi’s studies into an independent field of research and provided a methodological model for subsequent scholars.

In later periods, especially from the 1980s onward, the publication of K. Eraslan’s *Selections from the Divan-i Hikmat* marked a new stage in the reinterpretation of Yassawi’s hikmats, the systematization of manuscripts, and the development of textual scholarship. Through this work, Yassawi’s legacy was explored not only in historical and literary terms but also from the perspectives of Sufi studies and source criticism.

Since the 1990s, the study of Yassawi and, more broadly, Central Asian Sufi schools has acquired a transnational character. Turkish scholars have addressed issues such as the geographical diffusion of this heritage, the structure of Sufi orders, and their influence on the history of Turkic literature. At the same time, the Kubrawiyya and Naqshbandiyya traditions have also received sustained scholarly attention, reinforcing a comprehensive approach to the study of Central Asian Sufism.

As a result, the research tradition formed in Turkey has made it possible to interpret Central Asian Sufi schools not merely as a regional phenomenon, but as an integral part of the broader Turkic and Islamic cultural heritage. The findings achieved through source-based analysis, comparative literary studies, and historical-analytical approaches continue to constitute the scientific foundation for contemporary research on Yassawi studies and Central Asian Sufism.

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